

Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires

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Abstract

Previous atomistic simulations and experiments have shown an increased Young's modulus and yield strength of fivefold twinned (FT) face-centered cubic metal nanowires (NWs) when compared to single crystalline (SC) NWs of the same orientation. Here we report the results of atomistic simulations of SC and FT Ag, Al, Au, Cu and Ni NWs with diameters between 2 and 50 nm under tension and compression. The simulations show that the differences in Young's modulus between SC and FTNWs are correlated with the elastic anisotropy of the metal, with Al showing a decreased Young's modulus. We develop a simple analytical model based on disclination theory and constraint anisotropic elasticity to explain the trend in the difference of the Young's modulus between SC and FTNWs. Taking into account the role of surface stresses and the elastic properties of twin boundaries allows to account for the observed size effect in Young's modulus. The model furthermore explains the different relative yield strengths in tension and compression as well as the material and loading dependent failure mechanisms in FTNWs.

Keywords: Fivefold twinning, Numerical algorithms (C), Anisotropic material (B), Microstructures (A), Strengthening and mechanisms (A)

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1. Introduction

Metallic nanostructures have recently attracted a lot of interest due to their remarkable mechanical properties. Nanometer sized pillars, thin films, particles, rods or whiskers for example can show strengths which are significantly larger than those of the bulk material, often reaching values close to the computed theoretical values (Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Zhu and Li, 2010). Furthermore, the elastic response of nano sized structures was also reported to be different from the bulk behavior (Chen et al., 2012; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b). These differences are generally attributed to the absence of defects like dislocations or flaws and the high surface to volume ratio (Chen et al., 2012; Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b; Weinberger and Cai, 2012; Zhu and Li, 2010). Together, these effects can lead to changes in the dominant deformation mode, e.g., from dislocation mediated plasticity to deformation twinning (Amodeo et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2014; Oh et al., 2007; Sedlmayr et al., 2012).

Currently, nanostructures in which five twin segments are joined along a common quintuple line have become the focus of many investigations (Damm et al., 2011; Filleter et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2011; Jiang et al., 2013; Lucas et al., 2008; Monk et al., 2008; Niekiet et al., 2014; Sun et al., 2013a; Zhu et al., 2012). Such fivefold twinned (FT) structures are found in various classes of materials like face-centered cubic (fcc) and body centered cubic (bcc) metals, semiconductors and alloys, forming nano particles, rods and wires (Hofmeister, 2004). Fivefold twinned silver nanowires (NWs) in particular play an important role in flexible and stretchable electronics, e.g., as transparent electrodes in organic light emitting diodes and printed solar cells (Garnett et al., 2012; Hu et al., 2010; Krantz et al., 2011, 2012; Lee et al., 2008; Lim et al., 2012) or highly stretchable conductors in functional devices (Lee et al., 2012; Xu and Zhu, 2012; Yao and Zhu, 2015). The functionality and reliability in such applications depend critically on the mechanical properties of the NW network. In this context knowledge about the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires (FTNWs) is of fundamental importance, in particular as their properties are significantly different from their single crystalline (SC) counterparts. An increased stiffness and yield strength were for

29 example reported in tension (Filleter et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2012), bending (Jing et al.,
30 2006; Wu et al., 2005, 2006) and nanoindentation experiments (Lucas et al., 2008). Most
31 recently recoverable plasticity (Bernal et al., 2015; Qin et al., 2015) and strain hardening
32 (Narayanan et al., 2015) have been addressed. Many atomistic simulations were carried
33 out on various elements to elucidate the underlying reasons for these improved properties
34 (Bernal et al., 2015; Cao and Wei, 2006; Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al.,
35 2007; McDowell et al., 2008b; Narayanan et al., 2015; Qin et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2013a;
36 Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2014). A systematic study
37 comparing different fcc metals over a wide range of diameters is however lacking, and no
38 consensus has been reached on the underlying reasons for the changes in elastic properties
39 and the yield stress.

40 Here we present the result of atomistic studies of SC and FT Al, Ni, Cu, Ag and Au NWs
41 spanning diameters from 2 to 50 nm. The results are captured in a simple but comprehensive
42 model based on constraints due to the FT structure and anisotropic elasticity. It is able
43 to explain the differences in elastic and plastic response as well as failure mechanisms with
44 respect to single crystalline wires, and the trends for different fcc metals.

45 The paper is structured as follows: first we review the literature on FTNWs, focusing
46 on their morphology and its description in terms of disclinations and on their mechanical
47 properties. Then we present the methodology and the results of the simulations. In the dis-
48 cussion we propose a simple analytical model for the change in stress state of FTNWs under
49 uniaxial load and its dependence on the elastic anisotropy. We use this model to discuss the
50 simulation results and their relationship to experiments and to provide an outlook for the
51 use of FT structures in the context of strain engineering before closing with a summary.

52 **2. Morphology and mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires**

53 *2.1. Morphology and strain state*

54 FTNWs consist of five wedge shaped segments joined by $\{111\}$ -twin boundaries and
55 sharing a common $[101]$ -direction along the wire axis. An idealized structure of a FTNW is

56 shown in Fig. 1a), where also the coordinate system used throughout this work to describe a
57 twin segment is introduced. Such pentagonal shaped wires with $\{100\}$ surfaces are observed
58 in experiments, however with more rounded edges (Chen et al., 2004a,b; Gao et al., 2005;
59 Ni et al., 2005; Reyes-Gasga et al., 2006), but also round wires are frequently found (Chen
60 et al., 2004a; Lim et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2006). Joining five wedge shaped segments of
61 fcc crystal structure by $\{111\}$ -twin boundaries would lead to a gap of 7.35° , as the angle
62 between two $\{111\}$ -planes in cubic systems is 70.53° (see Fig. 1b)). FT structures therefore
63 are inherently strained to avoid this gap. As pointed out by De Wit (1972) the closure of
64 this gap can be described as a positive partial wedge disclination with its Frank vector $\vec{\omega}$
65 along the center line of the NW and its magnitude $\omega = 7.35^\circ$, as schematically shown in
66 Fig. 1b). The stress field produced by a wedge disclination with $\vec{\omega}$ parallel to the axis \vec{z}
67 of a cylinder with radius R can be derived using isotropic linear elasticity and cylindrical
68 coordinates to (Romanov and Vladimirov, 1992):

$$\sigma_{rr}(r, \theta) = D \ln\left(\frac{r}{R}\right), \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r, \theta) = D \left[\ln\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) + 1 \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{zz}(x, y) = \nu D \left[2 \ln\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) + 1 \right], \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = \sigma_{rz} = \sigma_{\theta z} = 0, \quad (4)$$

72 with $D = \omega\mu(1 + \nu)/2\pi$, where the shear modulus is denoted by μ and the Poisson's ratio
73 by ν . Johnson et al. (2007) were able to visualize the strain field in a FT Au nanoparticle
74 by strain mapping of a high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) image
75 which corresponds to the strain field of a central disclination. Recently it was shown by
76 directly comparing experimental X-ray diffraction data with atomistic calculations that the
77 complex strain field in Ag FTNW could indeed be explained by the presence of a central
78 disclination (Niekiel et al., 2014). Disclination theory has furthermore been used to address
79 the stability and relaxation mechanisms (Gryaznov et al., 1999; Kolesnikova and Romanov,
80 2007; Romanov et al., 1993) in FT structures as well as their growth mechanisms (Yasnikov
81 and Vikarchuk, 2007).

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a) the microstructure of fivefold twinned NWs and b) the compensation of the 7.53° misfit by a positive partial wedge disclination with Frank vector $\vec{\omega}$ at the quintuple line, a Cartesian coordinate system and respective crystallographic directions are drawn for the highlighted segment, c) illustration of sample geometry in simulations: cross sectional view of FT and SC NW indicating definition of diameter d , colored according to coordination number.

2.2. Elastic properties

Due to their small size, FTNWs are expected to show a similar increase in their Young's moduli with decreasing diameter as their SC counterparts (Diao et al., 2004; Dingreville et al., 2005; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b; Miller and Shenoy, 2000; Shankar and King, 2007). Currently, two models for the size effect are discussed: effects due to the different structure at the surface (Diao et al., 2004; Dingreville et al., 2005; Miller and Shenoy, 2000) and effects due to nonlinear elasticity resulting from a prestrain of the NWs caused by surface tension (Liang et al., 2005; Shankar and King, 2007). As pointed out by McDowell et al. (2008b), experiments show a size effect at much larger diameters than in atomistic simulations, indicating that other effects like the presence of surface layers, e.g. oxides, have to be taken into account to explain the increased Young's moduli in experiments.

Whether the elastic response of FTNWs differs from SCNWs with the same crystallographic orientation and diameter is currently under debate. Zhu et al. (2012) performed *in situ* tensile tests in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) on Ag FTNWs with diameters between 34 and 130 nm and found an increase in Young's modulus for diameters below 80 nm compared to bulk Ag with the same crystallographic orientation ($E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = 83.8$ GPa, see Tab.1). The highest measured Young's modulus was $E = 176$ GPa for a wire of diameter $d = 34$ nm. Similarly, Filletter et al. (2012) performed *in situ* tensile test in a transmission electron microscope (TEM) on Ag FTNWs with diameters ranging from 40 to 120 nm. They also found an increase of the Young's modulus for wires smaller than 55 nm, with the highest Young's modulus $E = 127 \pm 4$ GPa for the smallest nanowire ($d = 41.7$ nm). Using atomic force microscopy (AFM) bending tests Wu et al. (2006) found an average Young's Modulus of 102 ± 23 GPa for Ag FTNWs with diameters between 22 and 46 nm, which was however independent of the diameter. In all cases the FTNWs Young's moduli were not directly compared to SCNWs. A comparison with data for the Young's moduli of Ag SCNWs ($d = 20 - 140$ nm) obtained by Jing et al. (2006) using AFM bending test is not conclusive because of the large scatter in the data (see McDowell et al. (2008b) for a direct comparison of these data sets).

Molecular static (MS) simulations by McDowell et al. (2008b) on $\{110\}$ -oriented Ag wires

111 showed no significant effect of the FT nanostructure on the Young's modulus for wires with
112 diameters below 7 nm. This is in contrast to the MS simulations by Yoo et al. (2010) on
113 Ag and Cu FTNWs ($d = 2 - 21$ nm) which showed an enhanced Young's modulus for FT
114 compared to SC NWs. The magnitude of this effect was dependent on the used atomic
115 interaction potential. Yoo et al. (2010) attribute the increase in Young's modulus of FT
116 compared to the SC NWs to the compressional stress state at the center of FTNWs. Wu
117 et al. (2011) come to a similar conclusion from their MD simulations on fcc Fe FTNWs and
118 add that the central region of the NW not only behaves stiffer but even expands laterally
119 under longitudinal load. A generally increased Young's modulus of FT in comparison to SC
120 NWs was also reported in simulations by Wen et al. (2012) for Pt, Au, Ag, Cu, Ni and Pd
121 for NWs with a diameter of 4 nm, and for Ag FTNW of $d = 10$ nm diameter by Sun et al.
122 (2013b). Recently, Zheng et al. (2014) found in their MS simulations on Cu FTNW with
123 diameters ranging from $d = 6$ to 160 nm not only a similar increase of the Young's modulus
124 with decreasing diameter, but in addition for wire diameters larger than 80 nm a nearly
125 constant, increased Young's modulus of about 1.1 times the Young's modulus of SC Cu in
126 the same orientation. Although the size-dependent increase of E could be nicely fitted with
127 an empirical core-shell model, the reason for the size-independent increase of the Young's
128 modulus remains unclear.

129 *2.3. Yield stress and plastic deformation*

130 It is well known that the yield stress of metallic structures like pillars, thin films, particles,
131 rods or wires increases when their characteristic size is in the sub-micron range (Greer and
132 Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Weinberger and Cai, 2012). This "smaller is stronger" effect
133 has been attributed to the absence of pre-existing dislocations, truncation of dislocation
134 sources, dislocation source exhaustion, dislocation starvation and dislocation nucleation-
135 controlled plasticity (Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Weinberger and Cai, 2012).
136 The same mechanisms can be expected to be at work in FTNWs. However, how the presence
137 of the twin boundaries and the central disclination influences the yield stress has only recently
138 become the focus of experimental investigations and computer simulations (Cao and Wei,

139 2006; Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013; Leach et al., 2007; Narayanan
140 et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2013a,b; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011).

141 Direct experimental comparison of the plastic deformation of fivefold and single crys-
142 talline wires has only recently be done by Qin et al. (2015) focusing on remarkable plastic
143 strain recovery in Ag FTNWs. Similar findings have been reported by Bernal et al. (2015).
144 Wu et al. (2006) performed bending tests on Ag FTNWs with diameters between 10 and
145 15 nm before and after annealing using AFM. They report super elastic behavior followed by
146 brittle failure for the as prepared samples, whereas the thermally annealed wires showed a
147 decreased yield stress and a more ductile behavior, which was attributed to the elimination
148 of the FT structure. However, the resulting microstructure was not characterized, and the
149 yield stress was not determined.

150 The yield strength of Ag FTNWs under tension was addressed by Zhu et al. (2012)
151 using *in situ* tensile tests in the SEM. For diameters between 34 and 130 nm they observed
152 an increase in yield strength with decreasing diameter, which followed a power law with an
153 exponent of $n = -0.6$. Their highest measured yield strength of $\sigma_y^{\text{FT}} = 2.6$ GPa is close to the
154 theoretical yield strength of $\sigma_y^{\text{theo.}} = 3.5$ GPa as calculated using density functional theory
155 (DFT) by Ogata et al. (2004). The observed size effect was attributed to the increase in
156 Young's modulus with decreasing diameter. After the onset of yielding they observed strain
157 hardening, which is assigned to the presence of the FT microstructure. As the yield strain
158 is found to scale with the surface area, it was concluded that yielding is dominated by
159 dislocation nucleation from surface sources.

160 In their *in situ* TEM tensile tests on Ag FTNWs, Filleter et al. (2012) also measured
161 yield stresses around 3 GPa. However, they reported only a weak dependence of the yield
162 stress on the wire diameter. In contrast, the stress-strain curves in their *in situ* experiments
163 showed an interesting size-dependent strain hardening behavior, with thinner NWs showing
164 more pronounced strain hardening than thicker NWs. Filleter *et al.* could correlate the
165 strain hardening to the nucleation of multiple local plastic regions, in which the formation
166 of each new plastic region required a stress increase. Their atomistic simulations allowed
167 them to identify the formation of stacking fault decahedra (SFD) as important deformation

168 mechanism (Filleter et al., 2012). The size dependence of strain hardening in FTNWs was
169 picked up by Narayanan et al. (2015). Comparing experimental tensile tests and molecular
170 dynamics (MD) simulations, they showed that the twin boundaries obstructing surface nu-
171 cleation of dislocations gives rise to the observed size effect (Narayanan et al., 2015). Plastic
172 deformation of Ag FTNWs was also studied by AFM nanoindentation on the side surfaces
173 of the wire (Lucas et al., 2008). There, the formation of a neck and series of yielding events
174 is observed, however, no comparison with single crystalline wires were made.

175 The plastic deformation of FTNWs has been the subject of several atomistic studies
176 (Cao and Wei, 2006; Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013; Leach et al.,
177 2007; Sun et al., 2013a,b; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011). Higher yield stresses than for
178 single crystalline wires were found for the FTNWs in rectangular Cu-wires with a diameter
179 of $d = 8$ nm (Cao and Wei, 2006), round Ag-wires with $d = 7.5$ nm (Gao et al., 2012) and
180 $d = 5, 10, 20$ nm (Sun et al., 2013a,b), pentagonal Ag-wires ($d = 1.7 - 26.8$ nm) (Leach et al.,
181 2007), pentagonal Ag, Au, Cu, Ni, Pd and Pt wires ($d = 4$ nm) (Wen et al., 2012), as well
182 as round fcc-Fe wires ($d = 6 - 24$ nm) (Wu et al., 2011). The observed increase in yield
183 strength relative to the SCNWs varied for a given diameter ($d = 4$ nm) across the elements
184 from about 9% (Au) to about 31% (Ni,Cu) (Wen et al., 2012). The yield stress σ_y^{FT} of the
185 FTNWs as well as the ratio of σ_y^{FT} and the yield stress of the SCNWs σ_y^{SC} increased for
186 decreasing wire diameters (Leach et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2011). Interestingly, Sun et al.
187 (2013b) observed that Ag FTNWs with a diameter of $d = 20$ nm showed a lower yield
188 strength in compression compared to SCNWs, which was attributed to the already initially
189 existing compressive stress in the FTNW.

190 In contrast to SCNWs of identical crystallographic orientation, which under tension usu-
191 ally deform by twinning (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007; Park et al., 2006; Sedlmayr
192 et al., 2012), the FTNWs deformed by the nucleation of Shockley partial dislocations at
193 the surfaces (Bernal et al., 2015; Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007;
194 Narayanan et al., 2015; Wen et al., 2012). The twin boundaries were observed to act as
195 barriers to dislocation motion and the plastic deformation was much more localized along
196 the wires in the FT than in the SC NWs (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al.,

197 2007; Narayanan et al., 2015; Wen et al., 2012). The more localized deformation led to neck
198 formation and pronounced decreased ductility of the FTNWs. These localized regions often
199 consist of stacking fault or micro twin arrangements with fivefold symmetry (Filleter et al.,
200 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013).

201 Different models for the enhanced yield strength of FT in comparison to SC NWs have
202 been suggested in literature: the subdivision of the FTNWs by the twin boundaries is
203 supposed to give rise to Hall-Petch-like hardening (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007).
204 Furthermore, the nucleation sites for dislocations were different in the FT than in the SC
205 NWs, which might lead to higher activation energies. Leach et al. (2007) pointed out that
206 if the yield strain would be constant, the yield strength would need to be scaled according
207 to the increased Young's modulus.

208 **3. Methods**

209 Two types of simulations were carried out to characterize the mechanical properties of
210 FTNWs under uniaxial load. In the elastic regime, we used simulations with finite strain
211 increments and subsequent full energy minimization (often termed quasistatic simulations).
212 Additional MD simulations at constant temperature and strain rate were performed covering
213 the entire strain range until rupture. As reference, the same simulations were performed on
214 SCNWs. The atomic interaction was described by the embedded atom method (EAM),
215 using the potentials of Mishin for Al (Mishin et al., 1999), Ni (Mishin, 2004), Cu (Mishin
216 et al., 2001), Ag (Williams et al., 2006), and the potential of Park and Zimmerman (2005) for
217 Au. The 0 K lattice constants, elastic constants and the anisotropy ratio of these potentials
218 are provided in Tab. 1.

219 The geometry of the simulated $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented wires is shown in Fig. 1c). The SCNWs
220 have a hexagonal cross section, with four $\{111\}$ - and two $\{100\}$ -surfaces. The pentagonal
221 FTNWs are bordered by five $\{100\}$ -surfaces. In the following, the diameter d of the wires is
222 taken as the one corresponding to the largest circle inscribed to the cross section, see Fig.
223 1c). Periodic boundary conditions (pbc) were used along the direction of the wire axis, thus
224 simulating infinitely long NWs. The studied wires had diameters of $d = 6a$ to $122a$, (a being

Table 1: Lattice constant a , elastic constants C_{ij} and anisotropy ratio $A = (2 C_{44})/(C_{11} - C_{12})$ of the used EAM potentials and derived values used in the analytical framework (Poisson's ratio $\nu_{[101]}^{[ijk]}$ in $[ijk]$ direction for strain along $[101]$, unconstraint Young's modulus $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ in $[101]$ direction, Young's modulus in $[101]$ direction $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$, taking into account the constraint of constant wedge angle, critical tensile strain $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0)$ at which the Frank vector is zero, see Discussion, Sec. 5.2); lattice constants are given in Å, the units of elastic constants are GPa.

Element	a	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	A	$\nu_{[101]}^{[10\bar{1}]}$	$\nu_{[101]}^{[010]}$	$E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$	$E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$	$\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0)$
Ag ^a	4.09	124.3	93.9	46.4	3.05	-0.097	0.829	83.8	88.1	0.029
Al ^b	4.05	113.7	61.5	31.6	1.21	0.265	0.398	79.9	78.0	0.191
Au ^c	4.08	186.1	157.1	39.0	2.69	0.000	0.844	78.0	78.0	0.032
Cu ^d	3.62	169.9	122.7	76.2	3.23	-0.138	0.822	131.3	141.7	0.028
Ni ^e	3.52	241.5	150.7	127.3	2.80	-0.110	0.693	226.6	239.1	0.033

^a(Williams et al., 2006)

^b(Mishin et al., 1999)

^c(Park and Zimmerman, 2005)

^d(Mishin et al., 2001)

^e(Mishin, 2004)

225 the lattice constant, see Tab. 1), i.e from about 2 to 50 nm. For the quasistatic finite strain
 226 increment simulations, the length of the simulation cell along the wire axis was $l = 71 a/\sqrt{2}$.
 227 For the dynamic simulations at constant strain rate, wires with $d = 60 a$ and $l = 432 a/\sqrt{2}$
 228 resulting in an aspect ratio of about 5 were chosen. The initial configurations were relaxed
 229 using the fast inertial relaxation engine (FIRE) (Bitzek et al., 2006) while adjusting l to
 230 lead to a stress free sample.

231 To determine the linear elastic response of the wires under tensile loading, an iterative
 232 procedure is used. The simulation cell and all atomic positions are scaled linearly according
 233 to a strain increment of 2×10^{-6} and the energy is minimized using FIRE. The resulting
 234 configuration is scaled again, until an engineering strain of $\epsilon_{zz} = 10^{-4}$ was reached. In
 235 addition, wires with $l = 84 a/\sqrt{2}$, $d = 60 a$ were similarly deformed and subsequently relaxed
 236 in the range between $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.04$ and 0.07 , using a increment of 10^{-2} .

237 For the MD simulations at constant nonzero temperature, the wires were equilibrated
 238 for 40 ps at 300 K in the microcanonical ensemble followed by 80 ps using a combined Nosé-
 239 Hoover thermostat and barostat (Hoover, 1985) to allow for stress relaxation in the longitu-
 240 dinal direction. Tensile deformation was prescribed by homogeneously scaling the simulation
 241 box and atomic positions at each time step, corresponding to a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , while
 242 using the thermostat to keep the temperature at 300 K.

243 To describe the strain state in the NWs the atomic strain tensor (Shimizu et al., 2007)
 244 was used. The atomic stress tensor is calculated following the virial expression (Allen and
 245 Tildesley, 1987). The Young's modulus of the NWs was determined from the virial stress of
 246 the configuration in the longitudinal direction at the different states of applied strain. By
 247 fitting 3rd order polynomials to the extracted stress-strain response the Young's modulus
 248 is calculated as the coefficient of the linear term. The volume used in the calculation of
 249 the virial stress was taken as the product of length l and the cross sectional area A . The
 250 latter was defined as the sum over the area of each atom in the cross sectional plane. The
 251 area per atom was calculated for each atom by modifying the bulk equilibrium area per
 252 atom in a $\{110\}$ -plane with the local atomic strain state. For situations in which many
 253 atoms are subjected to large strains, as e.g., in the case of NWs with small diameters, this

254 correction provides significant improvement over the assumption of a constant cross sectional
 255 area per atom. For NWs with larger diameters the difference in total cross sectional area
 256 becomes negligible. This definition of the cross sectional area was also used to calculate the
 257 stress-strain curves from the virial stresses of the simulation box. The images of atomistic
 258 configurations in this work were created with AtomEye (Li, 2003) and ParaView (Sandia
 259 National Laboratory et al., 2000-2008).

260 4. Results

261 4.1. Quasistatic elastic loading

262 The resulting Young's moduli of the FT and SC NWs determined from the simulations
 263 with finite strain increments and subsequent energy minimization are shown in Fig. 2. The
 264 values have been normalized by the Young's modulus of the corresponding bulk crystal in
 265 the $\langle 110 \rangle$ -direction ($E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$) (see Tab. 1). To compare between the FT and the SC NWs, we
 266 introduce the diameter d^* , which is the equivalent diameter of a cylinder with cross sectional
 267 area of same magnitude. These diameters were normalized by the lattice constant a (see
 268 Tab. 1) to allow for a direct comparison of the different elements.

269 All SCNWs show an increase in Young's modulus with decreasing diameter, see Fig. 2a).
 270 The magnitude of this size effect however varies strongly for the different elements, and
 271 ranges from a very strong size effect for Au to a vanishing size effect in the case of Ni. Power
 272 laws of the form $Ax^n + B$ have been fitted to the data points, the resulting parameters
 273 are given in the inset table and are plotted as dashed lines in Fig. 2a). All elements show
 274 exponents close to $n = -1$, except for Ni, which shows no significant size dependence. The
 275 extrapolation for $d^*/a \rightarrow \infty$ yields $E_{[101]}^{\text{SC}}/E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} \rightarrow 1$ for all elements.

276 The situation is strikingly different for the case of the FTNWs shown in Fig. 2b). With in-
 277 creasing diameter, the Young's modulus $E_{[101]}^{\text{FT}}$ seems to level off at a constant value (between
 278 1.05 and $1.1E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ for Au, Ni, Ag and Cu) rather than to converge to $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ for $d^*/a \rightarrow \infty$.
 279 This suggests that the Young's modulus of FTNWs is fundamentally different from the
 280 Young's modulus of SCNWs, independent of diameter. Furthermore the Young's modulus

Figure 2: Size dependence of Young's moduli of simulated SC a) and FT b) NWs plotted over diameter of cylinder of same cross sectional area d^* normalized by the lattice constant a . Inset table in a) shows parameters of fitted power laws, which are plotted as dashed lines in a). The indicated errors are standard errors as determined by the fitting routine. Dashed lines in b) are guides to the eye connecting the single data points.

Figure 3: Dependence of the stress field on axial strain: magnitude of atomic stress in radial direction σ_{rr} and along the wire axis σ_{zz} for a) Ag and b) Al FTNWs ($d = 60a$) at different stages of tensile loading. Inversion of radial stress in Ag FTNW occurs at about $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ while this is not observed for Al in the shown strain range. Please note the different color scales for the different stress components and materials.

281 can increase (Au, Cu) with decreasing wire diameters as well as decrease (Ag, Ni), depending
 282 on the material. Similar to the SCNWs the Young's modulus can also be nearly independent
 283 of diameter and close to the bulk value. However, in the SCNWs this is the case for Ni, in
 284 the FTNWs it is the case for Al. Close inspection of the values for the Cu FTNWs reveal
 285 that $E_{[101]}^{\text{FT}}$ first shows a slight decrease with decreasing diameter before it starts to increase
 286 below $d^* \leq 16a$. Consequently, the behavior of $E_{[101]}^{\text{FT}}$ as function of diameter can not be
 287 described by a simple power law, as in the case of the SCNWs.

288 In addition to the stress state at zero load, the stress state for Al and Ag FTNWs with
 289 diameter $d^* = 60a$ was also determined at $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ and 0.06 . As can be seen from Fig. 3,
 290 the change in the values of the stress components is not homogeneous throughout the wire:

291 areas with higher stresses show larger changes in stress than the lower stressed areas closer
 292 to the surfaces. In the case of Ag (Fig. 3a)), the center of the wire, where the disclination
 293 is located, shows an inversion in sign of both, the radial and the axial stress, from highly
 294 compressive at zero strain over nearly zero stress to highly tensile at $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.06$. As the
 295 stress field is associated to the disclination in the center, this change in stress field would
 296 imply that the initially positive partial wedge disclination with $\omega = +7.35^\circ$ changes its
 297 Frank vector and ω becomes negative. The situation is however different in Al, see Fig. 3b).
 298 There, the most stressed areas show also the largest changes in stress, but the sign of the
 299 radial stress component does not change between $\epsilon_{zz} = 0$ and 0.06. It is important to note
 300 that the stress state in axial direction is in both cases the result of a superposition of the
 301 applied tensile strain ϵ_{zz} and the stress field of the disclination. This explains why in Al
 302 a change of sign of σ_{zz} is observed, while σ_{rr} does not change sign with increasing strain.
 303 In this case the initial compressive stress is compensated by the tensile stress due to ϵ_{zz} .
 304 The center of the FTNW where the compressive axial stress due to the disclination has its
 305 maximum displays therefore under tension lower stress levels than the outer regions. This
 306 is in contrast to the situation in Ag.

307 4.2. Tensile tests at constant temperature and strain rate

308 The results of the simulated tensile tests at 300 K and a strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of
 309 Ag and Al SC and FT NWs ($d = 60 a$, $l = 432 a/\sqrt{2}$) are shown in Fig. 4 and Tab. 2.
 310 Movies of the tensile tests are available in the supplementary material (movies M1-M4).
 311 As can be seen from the stress-strain curve in Fig. 4a) and Tab. 2, the differences between
 312 the Young's moduli of the FT and SC NWs observed in the quasistatic simulations at 0 K
 313 are still present in the dynamic simulations at 300 K. As typical for simulations of perfect,
 314 dislocation free NWs at the usual MD strain rates, all NWs show a high yield strength σ_y
 315 in the range of 2.8 to 3.2 GPa. The yield strength of the Ag FTNW is about 12% higher
 316 than for the SCNW, for the Al FTNW however, σ_y is around 3% smaller than that of the
 317 SCNW (see Tab. 2).

318 The onset of yielding is immediately followed by a sharp stress drop, succeeded by a

Figure 4: a) Engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of FT and SC NWs ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) ; Ag b) and Al c) FTNWs at different stages of tensile test, colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms are not shown), the pore formed in the Ag FTNW is indicated by the red arrow.

Table 2: Results of simulated tension and compression tests of nanowires ($d = 60 a, l = 432 a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K and a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} . Young’s modulus E , yield stress σ_y and strain at failure ϵ_f .

Sample	E / GPa	σ_y / GPa	ϵ_f /%
tension			
Ag FTNW	89.5	3.2	17
Ag SCNW	85.2	2.8	60
Al FTNM	80.6	3.0	19
Al SCNW	81.4	3.1	70
compression			
Ag FTNW	90.3	8.1	> 25
Ag SCNW	85.7	8.7	> 25

319 short increase in stress, after which the FTNWs rapidly fail, whereas the SCNWs deform
320 at a stress level around 0.8 GPa and attain significant strains, see also Fig. S2 in the
321 supplementary material. Before the onset of fracture, the flow stress of the FT is larger
322 than of the SCNWs. Again, this difference is more pronounced in Ag than in Al. The
323 fracture strains of the SCNWs are about four times higher than for the FTNWs. This
324 high ductility is caused by massive deformation twinning in both the Ag and Al SCNWs,
325 see movies M2 and M4. This deformation mode of $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented fcc SCNWs has been
326 thoroughly studied in the literature (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2014;
327 Park et al., 2006; Sedlmayr et al., 2012) and is therefore not further analyzed here.

328 In contrast, the FTNWs with the same orientation do not show massive deformation
329 twinning - only a couple of 2-3 layer twins are observed, which are confined to their twin
330 segments. Fig. 4b) and c) show configurations of the Ag and Al FTNWs after the onset
331 of yielding and after fracture. In the case of the FTNWs the deformation is initiated by
332 the nucleation of $\delta A(d)$ and $\alpha D(a)$ Shockley partial dislocations at the surfaces (Burgers
333 vectors are given in the usual Thompson tetrahedron notation (Hirth and Lothe, 1982)).

334 Transmission of these partial dislocations through the twin boundaries leads to fivefold
335 symmetric arrangement of stacking faults. In some cases also the nucleation of trailing
336 partial dislocations (e.g. $C\alpha(a)$ or $B\alpha(a)$) has been observed.

337 In both Ag and Al FTNWs, the deformation is localized in one region along the length of
338 the FTNWs, while other regions stay in the perfect FT configuration. One striking difference
339 between the two FTNWs is the formation of a pore in the Ag FTNW (indicated by the red
340 arrow in Fig. 4b)). This pore formed during complex dislocation processes at or close to
341 the quintuple line. No pore formation could be observed in the Al FTNW. The Ag FTNW
342 finally fractures at the pore, which grew over the course of the tensile test leading to a
343 particular fracture surface exhibiting a dimple. In contrast, only necking is observed in the
344 case of the Al FTNW.

345 4.3. Compression tests at constant temperature and strain rate

346 Dynamic compression tests at 300 K and a strain rate of 10^{-8} s^{-1} were carried out on Ag
347 FT and SCNWs with diameter $d = 60 a$ and length $l = 432 a/\sqrt{2}$. The corresponding stress-
348 strain curves are shown in Fig. 5a). The Young's moduli in compression are comparable to
349 the ones in tension, see Tab. 2. However, the compressive strain causes a stiffening already
350 for $\epsilon_{zz} < 0.01$, which explains the slightly increased Young's moduli compared to tension.
351 For larger strains the stiffening increases further as can be seen in the increasing slope of
352 the stress-strain curve, leading to overall higher stress values compared to the simulations
353 of tensile tests (compare Fig. 4).

354 Both, the SC and the FTNW yield at a more than 2.5 times higher stress than under
355 tensile loading. This large difference can be understood by considering that the Schmid
356 factor for the leading partial dislocation is a factor of two larger under tension than in
357 compression, leading to lower tensile stresses required to nucleate dislocations under tension
358 compared to compression (Lee et al., 2014). In contrast to the simulated tensile tests, the
359 FTNW has a *lower* yield stress under compression than the SCNW (see Fig. 4 and Tab. 2).

360 The deformation is in both cases carried by full dislocations, as indicated by the slip steps
361 and the bounded stacking faults in Fig. 5b). This is in accordance to the larger resolved

Figure 5: Results of the compression tests: a) stress-strain curve for Ag FT and SC NWs ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}a$); b) configuration of the SC and c) of the FTNW. Deformation is mainly caused by full dislocations leaving slip steps at the surfaces. In the FTNW additional extended partial dislocations on planes parallel to the compression axis are present (color coding according to the centrosymmetry parameter, only non-fcc atoms are shown).

362 shear stress on the trailing compared to the leading partial dislocation(Lee et al., 2014). A
363 peculiarity of the FTNW under compression is the occurrence of full dislocations as well as
364 extended stacking faults on glide planes parallel to the twin planes ((*b*) or (*c*)-planes), see
365 Figs. 5c). These dislocations either nucleate directly at the surface or cross-slip from the
366 (*a*) and (*d*)-planes onto the (*b*) or (*c*)-planes. It is important to note that dislocations on
367 these glide planes do not contribute to the longitudinal deformation of the wire under the
368 compressive load.

369 5. Discussion

370 The structure of the discussion is as follows: we start with examining the equilibrium
371 stress state in FTNWs and comparing it to disclination theory in Sec. 5.1 . In Sec. 5.2 we
372 develop a simple analytical model for the elastic response of FTNW under uniaxial load.
373 Based on this model the size independent differences in the Young’s modulus of FT and
374 SC NWs are discussed. Sec. 5.3 addresses atomistic effects and discusses the observed size
375 effects. In Sec. 5.4 we pick up the analytical model to explain the observations in the
376 plastic behavior of FTNWs, before comparing our results to the available experiment data
377 in Sec. 5.5.

378 5.1. Stress state of fivefold twinned nanowires

379 The atomic stresses in the cross section of an Ag FTNW are compared in Fig. 6 to the
380 stress state around a $\omega = 7.35^\circ$ wedge disclination according to Eqs. 1 - 4. In these isotropic
381 solutions, the Voigt average of the elastic constants of the Ag potential were used, leading
382 to $\mu = 33.9$ GPa and $\nu = 0.35$. As can be seen in Fig. 6, the stress state of the Ag FTNWs
383 compares well to the analytically expected stress state of a wedge disclination in an isotropic
384 material, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Both feature the highly compressive stress
385 state at the center of the NW, where the disclination is located. The stress components σ_{rr} ,
386 $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and σ_{zz} show a radial symmetric distribution with deviations at the twin boundaries
387 for the simulation results. Qualitatively, the overall stress state is similar for the different
388 potentials, and shows no significant change with diameter (not shown here).

Figure 6: Comparison of a) the stress state in the cross section of the relaxed Ag FTNW ($d = 60a$) and b) the analytical solution of the stress field of a wedge disclination ($\omega = 7.35^\circ$) at the center of a disk of isotropic material with elastic properties according to a Voigt average of the elastic constants of the Ag potential ($\mu = 33.9$ GPa, $\nu = 0.35$). The respective $\sigma_{ij} = 0$ level is plotted as black contour line.

389 A significant difference is the occurrence of a nonzero $\sigma_{r\theta}$ in the simulations, which would
 390 be expected to be zero according to the analytical solution, Eq. 4. The magnitude of $\sigma_{r\theta}$ is
 391 maximal at the intersection of the twin boundaries with the free surface, and has opposite
 392 signs in the adjoining crystallites. Corresponding shear strains $\epsilon_{r\theta}$ were also observed by
 393 Johnson et al. (2007) in HRTEM studies of a FT Au nanoparticle. The observed shear
 394 stresses are a direct consequence of the elastic anisotropy of the material and are therefore
 395 not captured by the isotropic elastic solution. At the twin boundaries, the crystallographic
 396 orientation changes, and so does the elastic response. However, at coherent interfaces like
 397 twin boundaries, displacements and strains parallel to the interface have to be continuous
 398 across the boundary (Sutton and Balluffi, 1995). Therefore, compatibility stresses arise at
 399 the twin boundaries to compensate the different elastic responses of the twin segments due to
 400 the strain caused by the gap closure (which corresponds to the presence of the wedge discli-
 401 nation). Although the presence of twin boundaries, free surfaces and anisotropic elasticity
 402 leads to deviations from the analytical isotropic solutions, Fig. 6 shows that disclination
 403 theory is useful to describe the stress and strain state in FTNWs.

404 5.2. Elastic response of fivefold twinned nanostructures:

405 *a simple analytical model and complementary finite element analysis*

406 For a single crystalline material, the Young's modulus in a certain direction can be
 407 determined from anisotropic elasticity theory, in which Hook's law takes the form (Hirth
 408 and Lothe, 1982)

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\epsilon_{kl} , \quad (5)$$

409 where σ_{ij} denotes the components of the stress tensor, C_{ijkl} represents the components of
 410 the tensor of elastic constants and ϵ_{kl} are the components of the strain tensor. As usual,
 411 the Einstein summation convention is used in the index notation of Hook's law, Eq. 5. The
 412 stresses and strains of interest here are described in the primed coordinate system shown in
 413 Fig. 1b) with axis $\mathbf{x}' = [10\bar{1}]$, $\mathbf{y}' = [010]$, $\mathbf{z}' = [101]$. The tensor of elastic constants in this
 414 coordinate system thus reads

$$C'_{ijkl} = M_{im}M_{jn}M_{ko}M_{lp}C_{mnop} , \quad (6)$$

415 with the rotation matrix corresponding to a 45° rotation around the y -axis

$$M_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

416 Using the Voigt notation (Hirth and Lothe, 1982) and the fact that cubic materials only have
 417 three independent elastic constants C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{44} , the stress tensor in the primed coordinate
 418 system for an arbitrary strain tensor can be calculated to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma'_{xx} \\ \sigma'_{yy} \\ \sigma'_{zz} \\ \sigma'_{yz} \\ \sigma'_{xz} \\ \sigma'_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\epsilon'_{xx}(C_{11}+C_{12}+2C_{44})}{2} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{yy} + \frac{\epsilon'_{zz}(C_{11}+C_{12}-2C_{44})}{2} \\ C_{12}\epsilon'_{xx} + C_{11}\epsilon'_{yy} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{zz} \\ \frac{\epsilon'_{xx}(C_{11}+C_{12}-2C_{44})}{2} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{yy} + \frac{\epsilon'_{zz}(C_{11}+C_{12}+2C_{44})}{2} \\ 2C_{44}\epsilon'_{yz} \\ \epsilon'_{xz}(C_{11} - C_{12}) \\ 2C_{44}\epsilon'_{xy} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

419 Under uniaxial strain in z -direction, a crystal in this orientation, which can freely relax in
 420 the orthogonal directions, will experience a tensile stress σ'_{zz} which can be calculated from
 421 Eq. 8 under the condition that $\sigma'_{xx} = \sigma'_{yy} = 0$. The constant relating stress and strain in
 422 this direction is the Young's modulus $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = \frac{\partial \sigma'_{zz}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}}$, which is that of a $\langle 110 \rangle$ oriented single
 423 crystal without constraints :

$$E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = \frac{4C_{44}(C_{11}^2 + C_{11}C_{12} - 2C_{12}^2)}{C_{11}^2 - 2C_{12}^2 + C_{11}(C_{12} + 2C_{44})} \quad (9)$$

424 This equation for the Young's modulus can alternatively be derived by taking the inverse of
 425 the S_{11} component of the compliance tensor in the appropriate coordinate system.

426 The Poisson's ratios in x - and y - direction for a crystal segment in the orientation of Fig. 1b),
 427 which is free to relax in the transversal directions ($\sigma'_{xx} = \sigma'_{yy} = 0$) while being deformed
 428 along the z -direction ($= [101]$), can be derived to

$$\nu_{[101]}^{[10\bar{1}]} = -\frac{\partial \epsilon'_{xx}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}} = \frac{-C_{11}^2 - C_{11}C_{12} + 2C_{12}^2 + 2C_{11}C_{44}}{-C_{11}^2 - C_{11}C_{12} + 2C_{12}^2 - 2C_{11}C_{44}}, \quad (10)$$

Figure 7: Young’s moduli determined by the simulations of the largest FT wires ($d = 122 a$) normalized by the according Young’s modulus of the bulk crystal $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ (Eq. 9) plotted over the anisotropy ratio A of the potential. Also shown are the results of FEA calculations and the analytical solution $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$ according to Eq. 12.

429

$$\nu_{[101]}^{[010]} = -\frac{\partial \epsilon'_{yy}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}} = \frac{4C_{12}C_{44}}{C_{11}^2 + C_{11}C_{12} - 2C_{12}^2 + 2C_{11}C_{44}}. \quad (11)$$

430 The Young’s moduli and Poisson’s ratios for the various potentials used in this work are
 431 given in Tab. 1.

432 In the following, size independent differences in Young’s moduli are discussed based on the
 433 values determined for the largest wire diameters ($d = 122 a$). The increase in the Young’s
 434 moduli of FT compared to SC NWs observed in the simulations is related to the material’s
 435 elastic anisotropy ratio $A = (2 C_{44})/(C_{11} - C_{12})$, see Fig. 7. The larger A , the higher the value
 436 of $E_{[101]}^{\text{FT}}/E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$. This can be easily understood: elastic anisotropy leads to different Poisson
 437 ratios in the directions orthogonal to the tensile axis (Eqs. 10 and 11, Tab. 1). However,
 438 different lateral expansions would violate the *constraint of constant wedge angle* imposed
 439 by the FT structure. The effect of this compatibility constraint becomes more pronounced
 440 the larger A . The constraint that the angle α between the $\{111\}$ twin boundaries of each
 441 segment has to stay constant leads to the condition that the strain in x - and y -direction have
 442 to be equal ($\epsilon'_{xx} = \epsilon'_{yy}$). Assuming that crystal segments are able to relax in the y -direction
 443 (free surface, $\sigma'_{yy} = 0$), the Young’s modulus under this constraint, $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$, can be derived

444 to

$$E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}} = \frac{(C_{11} + 2C_{12})(C_{11} - C_{12} + 2C_{44})}{2(C_{11} + C_{12})}. \quad (12)$$

445 Comparing the Young's moduli of FTNWs determined from simulations with $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$
446 from Eq. 12 in Fig. 7 shows that the overall trend of increasing Young's modulus with
447 increasing A is captured by this simple expression. However, Eq. 12 underestimates the
448 actual increase in Young's moduli of FTNWs compared to the bulk single crystal value.
449 This indicates that the actual constraints in FTNWs are more complex. The segments do
450 not deform independently of each other and compatibility stresses need to be taken into
451 account.

452 To include the effects of the constraints due to the fivefold twinned structure in more
453 detail, finite element (FE) calculations were performed using cylindrical FTNWs and lin-
454 ear anisotropic elasticity with the values of C_{ij} according to the EAM potentials, Tab. 1
455 (for detailed information on the FE calculations see the supplementary material). The so
456 determined values for the Young's moduli are also shown in Fig. 7. As can be seen, the
457 FE analysis consistently *overestimates* the increase in Young's moduli of FTNWs compared
458 to the bulk value. However, as the FE analysis does not include nonlinear elasticity, size
459 effects or other atomistic effects, the calculations unequivocally show that the increase of
460 the Young's modulus in FTNWs can be explained as a consequence of the geometrical
461 constraints imposed by the five-fold twinned microstructure. The differences between the
462 Young's moduli determined by the FE calculations and the predictions made by Eq. 12 are
463 a result of the fact that the FE analysis takes into account the inhomogeneous stress and
464 strain distribution and thus allows for compatibility stresses. In contrast, the differences to
465 the atomistic calculations as well as the their dependence on the wire diameter have to be
466 of atomistic origin.

467 5.3. Atomic scale stress-strain response and size effects

468 The FT as well as the SC NWs show a clear dependence of their Young's moduli on the
469 wire diameter, see Fig. 2. Whereas FTNWs show, depending on the material, decreasing
470 as well as increasing Young's moduli with decreasing wire diameter, all SCNWs with the

471 exception of Ni show an increase of the Young's modulus with decreasing diameter. This
472 observation follows the trend described in the literature, e.g., for simulations of Cu (Liang
473 et al., 2005) and Ag (McDowell et al., 2008b; Yoo et al., 2010) $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented SCNWs.
474 The size effect is commonly ascribed to the increase in the surface to volume ratio with
475 decreasing diameter (Diao et al., 2004; Dingreville et al., 2005; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell
476 et al., 2008a,b; Miller and Shenoy, 2000; Shankar and King, 2007; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al.,
477 2010). This is in agreement with our result that (with the exception of Ni) the increase of the
478 Young's modulus is proportional to $(d^*)^n$ with $n \approx -1$ (see Fig. 2a)), which is to be expected
479 as the volume to surface ratio for the representative cylinder scales as $(d^*)^{-1}$ (Miller and
480 Shenoy, 2000). The influence of the surface on the Young's modulus is commonly attributed
481 to surface stresses (Liang et al., 2005): relaxation of these stresses leads to a shortening
482 of the wire until the compressive stress of the atoms inside the wire balances the surface
483 stresses (leading to a wire which, averaged over the cross section, is stress free). This results
484 in initial compressive prestrain for the atoms inside the wire, which in turn is assumed to
485 lead to an increase of the Young's modulus due to nonlinear elastic effects (Liang et al.,
486 2005). The general increase of the Young's modulus with increasing compressive strain can
487 also be directly evidenced in Fig. 5a).

488 Fig. 8a) shows that indeed the SCNWs shrink during relaxation. The increase in Young's
489 modulus is in turn linearly related to this prestrain, as shown in Fig. 8c). The situation is
490 different in the FTNWs, where only wires with a small diameter shrink during relaxation,
491 whereas relaxation leads to a *tensile* prestrain in the wires with larger diameters due to
492 the stress field of the disclination, see Fig. 8b). No general trend can be inferred for the
493 dependence of the Young's modulus of FTNWs on their prestrain. Depending on the material,
494 decreasing as well as increasing or unchanged Young's moduli are found, see Fig. 8c).

495 The effect of strain state on the Young's modulus can also be directly determined by
496 calculating the local tensor of elastic constants from the second order partial derivatives of
497 the potential energy of the atoms with respect to the interatomic distances and the local
498 atomic volume, see e.g. (Alber et al., 1992). Within the EAM formalism, these derivatives
499 can be obtained by numerical differentiation of the potential functions. The local atomic

Figure 8: Prestrain along the wire axis induced during the relaxation of a) SC and b) FT NWs as function of their diameter d^* ; c) relative change of the Young's modulus of FT and SC NWs compared to the bulk value as function of the prestrain induced during relaxation.

500 volume required for the calculation of the local elastic constants is determined by a Voronoi
 501 tessellation. Here, the “local Young’s modulus” in [101] direction is then taken as the
 502 inverse of the component S'_{11} of the full compliance tensor in the appropriate coordinate
 503 system. Fig. 9a) shows that when the length of the Ag SCNW is held constant according
 504 to the equilibrium lattice parameter, the local Young’s modulus is rather homogeneous in
 505 the wire cross section and its average fits nicely the calculated value of 83.8 GPa for bulk
 506 Ag (see Tab. 1). When the axial stress due to the surface stresses is allowed to relax, the
 507 length of the wire decreases by 1% and the local Young’s moduli increase to an average of
 508 $\bar{E}_{\text{local}} = 84.9$ GPa (Fig. 9a), right). This value is slightly larger than the Young’s modulus
 509 determined from the quasistatic tensile test of this wire $E = 84.1$ GPa.

510 The calculation of the local elastic constants of the Ag FTNW however shows a significant
 511 *reduction* of the local Young’s modulus: when the stress along the wire axis is allowed to
 512 relax, the wire length increases by 2.7% and the average local Young’s modulus decreases to
 513 $\bar{E}_{\text{local}} = 70.1$ GPa, see Fig. 9b). This is much smaller than the Young’s modulus determined
 514 from the quasistatic tensile test of this wire $E = 90.8$ GPa. The decreased averaged local
 515 Young’s modulus can be explained by the Poisson’s ratio derived in Eq. 10: Closure of
 516 the 7.35° gap in the FT structure (see Fig. 1b)) requires a tensile strain in $[10\bar{1}]$ -direction
 517 (leading to the tensile stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ in shown in Fig. 6), which according to Eq. 10 in turn induces
 518 tensile strain in the axial [101]-direction. As a compressive strain leads to an increase in
 519 Young’s modulus due to nonlinear elastic effects (Liang et al., 2005), a tensile strain should
 520 correspondingly lead to its decrease.

521 The local Young’s modulus (Fig. 9b)) clearly shows that contrary to SCNWs the increase
 522 in Young’s modulus in axial direction in FTNWs is *not* due to the strain state of the atoms
 523 inside the wires. This is in contrast to the work of Yoo et al. (2010), who found a locally
 524 increased elastic modulus in FTNW. Their calculation of the local Young’s modulus is
 525 however based on applying a tensile strain on the wire and fitting a second order polynomial
 526 to the virial stress - global strain curve. By this approach, the stress field due to the
 527 disclination gets mixed into the calculations, and the result does therefore not correspond
 528 to a local Young’s modulus.

Figure 9: Local Young's modulus determined from the local elastic constants for a) the FT and b) the SC Ag NW with the largest diameter. Left: relaxed configuration without box relaxation, right: with stress relaxation in axial direction. In the case of the SCNW, stress relaxation leads to a compressive strain and an increase of E . For the FTNW, relaxation of axial stresses leads to a tensile strain and a decrease of E ; c) shows the normalized Young's moduli of Ag and Ni SCNWs as function of their diameter as determined by the quasistatic tensile tests and by averaging over the local elastic constants.

529 The change in the local Young's modulus due to the strain state is however not the only
530 atomistic effect. Fig. 9c) compares the increase of the Young's moduli as determined from
531 the quasistatic tensile tests to the average of the local Young's moduli of Ag and Ni SCNWs.
532 It can be seen that the average local Young's modulus \bar{E}_{local} is always larger than the Young's
533 modulus determined by the tensile tests. The calculation of \bar{E}_{local} does not include surface
534 atoms, as their local volume can not be defined by a Voronoi tessellation. Consequently,
535 the difference between \bar{E}_{local} and the Young's moduli determined from tensile tests must be
536 caused by significantly lower contribution from the surface atoms to the elastic response of
537 the NW. This is in agreement with the observation of Liang et al. (2005) that "the nanowire
538 surface is always softer than the (equivalent) bulk" and the mostly negative values of the
539 surface elastic modulus tensor as determined by Shenoy (2005). Fig. 9c) shows that in the
540 case of Ni, the influence of the surface elastic modulus can be so large that it offsets the
541 increase of the local Young's modulus due to the surface-stress induced compressive prestrain
542 (Fig. 8).

543 Whereas the increase of the Young's modulus of SCNWs is solely caused by atomistic
544 effects, namely the surface stress and the surface stiffness, the size-dependence of the elastic
545 response of FTNWs is more complex. The constraint by the fivefold twinned structure leads
546 to a size-independent increased apparent Young's modulus, but also to a decrease in the local
547 elastic constants. The surface stress and surface stiffness effects are similar to the SCNWs,
548 although with different magnitudes, as the FTNWs possess only $\{100\}$ surfaces compared
549 to the $\{111\}$ and $\{100\}$ surfaces of the SCNWs. The compression of the wire by the surface
550 stresses has to act against the tensile prestrain due to the fivefold twinned structure, so
551 that only the wires with very small diameters experience a compressive prestrain. Whether
552 the increase in local elastic constants due to these compressive strains can lead to a further
553 increase in the Young's modulus then depends on the magnitude of the surface stiffness.

554 In summary, the size dependence of the apparent Young's modulus of FTNW in axial
555 direction depends on the complex interplay between several factors, which can strongly
556 depend on the material: (i) the constraints caused by the FT structure (size independent);
557 (ii) the dependence of the local elastic response on the inhomogeneous strain field caused by

558 the central disclination and the surface stresses; and (iii) the surface elastic modulus, which
559 depends on the crystallographic orientation of the surfaces. The resulting size dependence of
560 the apparent Young's modulus is therefore complex, and dependent on the material, E can
561 increase, decrease or even first decrease and then increase with decreasing diameter as shown
562 in Fig. 2. Our results thus clearly show that although the size dependent elastic modulus
563 of FTNWs might in some cases be described by a purely empirical core-shell composite
564 structure model (Zheng et al., 2014), such a model can not be generally applied to FTNWs
565 and does not capture the underlying physics.

566 *5.4. Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the plastic deformation in fivefold twinned nanowires*

567 The example of the Ag FTNW shown in Fig. 3a) demonstrates that with increasing
568 elastic tensile strain the stress state due to the disclination changes, which can even lead
569 to an inversion from compressive to tensile radial stress close to the quintuple line. For the
570 interpretation of the stress fields shown in Fig. 3 the applied axial strain has to be taken
571 into account, which leads to a superimposed homogeneous tensile stress in σ_{zz} of rising
572 magnitude with increasing tensile strain.

573 The framework developed in Sec. 5.2 can be used to explain the observed phenomenon. Due
574 to elastic anisotropy, the Poisson's ratios are different in the $[10\bar{1}]$ and the $[010]$ directions,
575 leading to a contraction of the segments in the direction of the surface normals and an
576 expansion orthogonal to the surface normal and the wire axis. This changes the angle α in
577 Fig. 1b) and thus the misfit $2\pi - 5\alpha$ between the twin segments, which has to be compensated
578 by the partial wedge disclination. The magnitude of the required partial wedge disclination
579 ω can therefore be expressed via the transversal Poisson's ratios as function of the applied
580 uniaxial elastic strain ϵ_{zz} as

$$\omega(\epsilon_{zz}) = 2\pi - 10 \arctan \left(\frac{1 - \nu_{[10\bar{1}]}^{[10\bar{1}]} \epsilon_{zz}}{\sqrt{2} (1 - \nu_{[10\bar{1}]}^{[010]} \epsilon_{zz})} \right). \quad (13)$$

581 This function is plotted in Fig. 10, using the Poisson's ratios calculated from the elastic
582 constants of the potentials according to Eqs. 10 and 11 (see Tab. 1 for the numerical
583 values).

Figure 10: Plot of $\omega(\epsilon_{zz})$ after equation 13 using Poisson's ratios of the used potentials.

584 An inversion, i.e. a change of sign, of the stress field caused by the disclination takes place
 585 when the Frank vector changes its sign, as the stresses depend linearly on the Frank vector
 586 (compare Eqs. 1-4). The critical strain for inversion is characterized by the Frank vector
 587 becoming zero $\omega(\epsilon_{zz}) = 0$, which corresponds to a wedge angle of the segments of exactly
 588 $\alpha = 72^\circ$. The elastic strain $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0)$ for which this is expected to take place according to
 589 Eq. 13 is provided in Tab. 1.

590 As shown in Fig. 3, the observed stress inversion in Ag at $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ agrees well with
 591 $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0) = 0.029$ predicted by Eq. 13. For Al, no similar inversion is observed in the range
 592 from $\epsilon_{zz} = 0$ to 0.06, which agrees with the much larger elastic strain of $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0) = 0.19$
 593 required for the Frank vector to become zero.

594 The stress state of a uniaxially strained wire containing a partial wedge disclination
 595 along its axis thus does *not* correspond to a superposition of a homogeneous uniaxial stress
 596 and the stress field of the disclination at zero applied strain. Instead the stress field of the
 597 disclination with an elastic *strain dependent Frank vector* according to Eq. 13 needs to be
 598 taken into account in determining the overall stress state.

599 The uniaxial tension and compression tests demonstrate clearly the importance of the
 600 strain-dependent stress field of the disclination for the plastic deformation: Under tension,
 601 the Ag wire which shows a inversion from compressive to tensile radial stress at the quintuple

602 line fails by void formation. In contrast, the Al FTNW without such stress inversion fails by
 603 necking (Figs. 3 and 4). Under compression, dislocations do not only glide on the slip system
 604 with the highest Schmid factor, but form structural dislocations on glide planes with zero
 605 Schmid factor to relieve the increasing stress field of the disclination (Fig. 5). Predicting
 606 the activity of a certain slip system in FTNWs requires the calculation of the resolved shear
 607 stress τ from the local stress tensor, including the strain- and position-dependent stress due
 608 to the disclination, and not just the Schmid factor. Fig. 11b) shows such a calculation of τ
 609 for the structural partial dislocation $C\beta(b)$ leading to the extended stacking faults visible in
 610 Figs 5c) and 11a). At $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ the resolved shear stress vanishes, because the magnitude
 611 of the disclination in Ag FTNWs becomes negligible as discussed above. At equilibrium
 612 $\epsilon_{zz} = 0$ there is a notable resolved shear stress on the partial dislocation which increases
 613 dramatically when the wire is compressed elastically to $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.03$.

614 So far, under tension only increased yield strengths of FT compared to SC NWs were
 615 reported in the literature on atomistic simulations of Cu, Ag and Pt wires (Cao and Wei,
 616 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2013b; Wen et al., 2012). Fig. 4 and
 617 Tab. 2 show a similar increase in yield strength for the Ag FTNW ($d = 60a$) under tension.
 618 Our simulations however demonstrate clearly that the FT structure does not automatically
 619 lead to a strengthening of the wire: the Al FTNW shows a small decrease of σ_y^{FT} when
 620 compared to σ_y^{SC} and under compression the Ag FTNW has a 7% lower yield strength than
 621 the SCNW, see Tab. 2.

622 In literature the increased yield strength is commonly attributed to the enhanced stiffness
 623 of the FTNWs (Leach et al., 2007; Wen et al., 2012) and the fact that dislocation nucleation
 624 from corners is prevented by the internal twin boundaries (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al.,
 625 2012; Leach et al., 2007). However, it is evident from our simulations that in addition the
 626 strain-dependent stress field at the nucleation site due to the disclination has to be taken
 627 into account. The superposition of uniaxial tensile stress and disclination stress field leads
 628 to an inhomogeneously increasing tensile stress in the cross section. This is shown in Fig. 3.
 629 In the case of Ag, the increase of σ_{zz} is more pronounced in the center of the wire than at the
 630 surfaces, whereas in Al it is the other way around and the stress is increased at the surface

Figure 11: a) Configuration of Ag FTNW at $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.06$ with structural dislocations indicated by red arrows. Atoms are colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown). The inset shows the orientation of Thompson tetrahedra of the segments of the multiply twinned geometry used in the notation, b) resolved shear stress acting on the $C\beta$ partial dislocations in dependence of ϵ_{zz} , c) von Mises stress within Ag FT and SC NW ($d = 60a$) for compression $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.05$ (left) and tension $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.05$ (right) (static simulation, surface atoms have been removed).

631 where the dislocations nucleate. To discuss the observation of structural dislocations in
632 compression tests, the von Mises stress is compared for the Ag FT and SCNW at $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.05$
633 and $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.05$ in Fig. 11c). It can be seen, that under tension the von Mises stress in the
634 FTNW is only slightly increased close to the center of the $\{100\}$ surfaces compared to the
635 overall stress state in the SCNW. Under compression, however, the von Mises stress in the
636 FTNW is locally much higher than in the SCNW.

637 The difference in yield stress between the SCNWs and FTNWs should in conclusion depend
638 in a non-trivial way on the specific material and the shape of the wire. E.g., on the differences
639 in the energy barrier to nucleate dislocations from different surfaces versus edges, and via
640 Eqs. 13 and 1 - 4 on the elastic constants and elastic anisotropy, which determine the stress
641 state of the nanowire containing a disclination.

642 *5.5. Relationship to experiments*

643 At the time of writing, only tensile tests on Ag FTNWs without direct comparison to
644 SCNWs (Filleter et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2012) were reported in the literature, with the
645 exception of the recent work by Qin et al. (2015), which however focuses on recoverable
646 plasticity. The large increase of the Young's modulus by 50-80% for wire diameters of
647 the order of 40 nm reported by Zhu et al. (2012) and Filleter et al. (2012) is not found
648 in our simulations, where wires of similar diameter show only an increase of about 8%.
649 The uncertainty in Young's modulus might possibly be attributed to errors, e.g. in the
650 determination of the cross sectional area in the experiments. However, Filleter et al. (2012)
651 performed a careful error analysis, which included the effect of the carbon coating layer and
652 determined their systematic error to be about 20%.

653 Atomistic simulations have their own set of limitations like the small scales and short
654 times which can be simulated. In particular, the results depend critically on the quality
655 of the used potentials. Although EAM potentials are fitted to the surface energies, surface
656 stress and stiffness are usually not considered in the development of potentials. They might
657 therefore fail to quantitatively reproduce the size effect in elastic properties of nanowires.
658 However, the analytical framework developed to explain the size independent differences in

659 Young's modulus between FT and SC NWs and the strain dependent Frank vector is solely
660 based on linear anisotropic elasticity. Predictions based on this model should therefore be
661 independent of the details of the potentials and experimentally testable.

662 Currently, only increased Young's moduli compared to single crystals have been reported
663 in the literature (Filleter et al., 2012; McDowell et al., 2008b; Sun et al., 2013b; Wen et al.,
664 2012; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2012). However, for
665 materials with low anisotropy ratio, like Al, our model predicts a decrease of the Young's
666 modulus for (large) FTNWs. Al FTNWs have not been reported in the literature, but
667 Platinum FT nanorods exist (Hofmeister, 2004). According to its elastic constants ($C_{11} =$
668 346.7 GPa, $C_{12} = 250.7$ GPa, $C_{44} = 76.5$ GPa, $A = 1.6$ (Macfarlane and Rayne, 1965)), our
669 model would predict a significant decrease of the Young's modulus from $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = 185.3$ GPa
670 to $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}} = 176.7$ GPa for Pt FTNW. This prediction deviates from the enhanced Young's
671 modulus of FTNWs compared to SCNWs found in the atomistic simulations of Wen et al.
672 (2012). However, taking into account the size effect on the Young's modulus (compare
673 Fig. 2) the diameters of the NWs used in their study ($d = 4$ nm) do not allow to discuss the
674 fundamental, size-independent differences in elastic behavior of FT and SC NWs.

675 The formation of voids under tension, as observed in our simulations of Ag FTNWs, was
676 not reported by Filleter et al. (2012). However, their FTNWs yielded at strains of about
677 3%, just about the strain where according to our calculations the inversion in radial stress
678 should take place (Fig. 10). Experiments on FTNWs with better surface quality and a
679 lower misalignment angle might be able to achieve larger elastic strains and thus show void
680 formation. Alternatively, materials with higher anisotropy ratio, which should show stress
681 inversion at lower elastic strains, could be used to test the hypothesis of stress inversion in
682 FTNWs upon tension.

683 **6. Outlook**

684 The unique microstructure of FTNWs opens up new routes for strain-engineering of
685 materials properties (Li et al., 2014). For example by alloying with elements which segregate
686 to the compressive strain field of the disclination, changes of the disclination stress field

687 with tensile strain would require more energy, thereby additionally stiffening the wire. In
688 semiconductors, the large strains at the disclination core could furthermore lead to different
689 band gaps in the wire centre compared to the outer wire. The leverage effect of the joined
690 twins, which, due to the anisotropy in the lateral expansion amplifies the effect of uniaxial
691 strain in the center of the wire, would allow for a highly sensitive tuning of the electronic
692 and optoelectronic properties of such wires.

693 **7. Summary**

694 In summary, we have presented the results of atomistic simulations of the stress-strain
695 response of Ag, Al, Au, Cu and Ni $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented fivefold twinned and single crystalline
696 nanowires with diameters between 2 and 50 nm. Whereas the single crystalline nanowires
697 show an increase of the Young's modulus with decreasing diameter compared to a bulk
698 crystal of identical orientation, the situation is more complex in the case of fivefold twinned
699 nanowires: for large diameters all materials show an increased Young's modulus indepen-
700 dent of the diameter, whereas for smaller diameters decreasing as well as increasing Young's
701 moduli were observed, depending on the material. Furthermore, under tensile load Ag five-
702 fold twinned nanowires show an increased yield strength compared to their single crystalline
703 counterparts and fail by formation and growth of pores in the center of the wire, whereas
704 the fivefold twinned Al nanowires show a decrease in yield stress and fail by necking. Under
705 compression, the fivefold twinned Ag nanowire however shows a lower yield stress compared
706 to the corresponding single crystalline wire.

707 The differences in Young's moduli can be rationalized by taking into account the compat-
708 ibility constraint imposed by the fivefold twinned structure and the anisotropy in Poisson's
709 contraction on top of the size effects due to surface stresses and surface stiffness. The
710 anisotropy in Poisson's contraction can be used to calculate the strength of the central par-
711 tial wedge disclination, i.e., its Frank vector, as function of uniaxial strain. The plastic
712 deformation of fivefold twinned structures depends critically on the local stress field which
713 is a combination of the applied load and the strain-dependent stress field of the disclination.
714 Depending on the elastic anisotropy, this can lead to a stress-inversion from compressive to

715 tensile radial stress in the center of the fivefold twinned wires under tensile load, causing the
716 pore formation observed in the fivefold twinned Ag nanowire, to an increased or decreased
717 yield stress compared to single crystalline nanowires, depending on the elastic anisotropy of
718 the material and the loading direction, as well as to the formation of structural dislocations
719 under compression.

720 The framework of constraint anisotropic elasticity in fivefold twinned nanowires devel-
721 oped in this paper allows to calculate the stress state within these wires as function of applied
722 strain, and thus to predict their plastic response. In anisotropic elastic materials, the fivefold
723 twinned structure acts as a lever by which one can control the stress state within nanowires
724 by the application of external strain, thus opening up new possibilities for strain-engineering
725 of materials properties.

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Supplementary Material for: Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires

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1. Finite Element Calculations

The analytical model based on the constraint of a *constant wedge angle* does not take into account additional compatibility constraints or inhomogeneous stress/strain distribution within the twin segments. Therefore, finite element (FE) calculations have been performed utilizing anisotropic linear elasticity in *Abaqus 6.12*. The FTNWs have been modeled as cylinders (diameter 30 nm, length 20 nm) exhibiting a circular cross section subdivided into five segments with local orientation corresponding to that of fivefold twins. Symmetry boundary conditions have been utilized to simulate infinitely long NWs. 101590 hexahedral elements (C3D8R) have been used to mesh the structure with 10159 elements in the cross section and 10 subdivisions along the wire axis. The tensile test was simulated by stepwise displacement of one end for an engineering strain of up to 10 %. The anisotropic elastic constants of the EAM potentials used in the main work have been used as material parameters to allow a direct comparison of MS simulations, analytical model and FE calculations.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of stress in wire axis direction σ_{zz} for a Ag FTNW at 10% tensile strain. As can be seen the stress distribution is homogeneous along the wire axis (due to the symmetry) but clearly inhomogeneous in the cross section. The elastic response

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of the FTNWs has been quantified from the FE calculations determining the Young's modulus from the engineering stress-strain behavior. The strain has been determined from the applied displacement, the stress has been determined summing the forces on the nodes in the cross section and dividing it by the cross sectional area.

Tab. 1 summarizes the results of FE calculations using the different material parameters. The values have been plotted in comparison to the analytical model and MS simulations in Fig. 7 in the main manuscript. As discussed there, the FE calculations solely represent the impact of the geometrical constraint and does not include any effect due to size effect, prestrain and nonlinearity as well as surfaces or interfaces.

Figure 1: Finite element model of the FTNW showing the stress in tensile direction of a Ag FTNW at 10% tensile strain.

Table 1: Results on elastic response of FTNW from FE calculations, E_{zz}^{FEM} in GPa.

Element	E_{zz}^{FEM}
Ag	94.9
Al	80.1
Au	87.0
Cu	149.8
Ni	247.9

2. Tensile tests

Fig. 2 shows the engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of Ag and Al FT and SC NWs plotted up to the failure of the SCNWs.

Figure 2: Engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of FT and SC NWs ($d = 60a$, $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$).

2.1. Movies

- M1.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Ag FTNW ($d = 60a$, $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.

- M2.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Ag SCNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.
- M3.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Al FTNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.
- M4.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Al SCNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.